

INSTITUTE OF NUCLEAR PHYSICS OF THE POLISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCES

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Anti-discrimination provisions are now more often included in higher education institutions' (HEI) policies than they were a few years ago. While the process of counteracting gender-based violence (GBV) in Polish academia started in 2010 with the establishment of the Rector's Committee for Preventing Discrimination at the University of Warsaw,¹ in recent years, many Polish universities have adopted measures designed to counteract discrimination in the workplace. They are usually part of the HEIs' internal regulations,^{2,3} but there are exceptions to this rule. Some more progressive HEIs develop and implement (internal) anti-mobbing and anti-discrimination procedures. On the one hand, this trend is an effect of the European Union's policies (i.e. the European Charter & Code for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers) and funding programmes (i.e. Horizon 2020), which aim to foster gender equality change by facilitating the development and implementation of gender equality measures and plans in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) (for example, GENERA, ACT, and MindTheGEP projects carried out at the Jagiellonian University in Krakow).^{4,5} On the other hand, publicising cases of discrimination against employees or students and reports confirming the existence of harassment at Polish public universities^{6,7,8} has resulted in the development of preventive actions to ensure the safety and security of RPO communities. In addition, the Ombudsperson had made several official appeals to the Conference of Rectors of Academic Schools in Poland (CRASP) and many ministries of the Polish government (i.e. in 2016 and 2019) and has asked them to adopt programmes to ensure the implementation of internal anti-discrimination procedures, and to take

¹ Fuszara, M. (2012). *Raport z prac Komisji Rektorskiej ds. Przeciwdziałania Dyskryminacji w kadencji 2008 – 2012*. Warszawa: Uniwersytet Warszawski. <http://www.rownowazni.uw.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/sprawozdanie-komisji-2008-2012.docx/>.

² Sierpowski, P. (2020, January 24). *Tackling gender inequalities at universities in Poland*. Gender Equality in Central and Eastern Europe Community of Practice. <https://geincee.act-on-gender.eu/Blog/tackling-gender-inequalities-universities-poland>.

³ Teutsch A., Stoch, M., & Kozakoszczak, A. (2017a). *Ramy prawne zjawiska dyskryminacji i przemocy motywowanej uprzedzeniami oraz możliwości reakcji na nie z wykorzystaniem instrumentów prawnych*. Kraków: Fundacja Autonomia. <https://bezpieczni.uj.edu.pl/documents/136167082/13991933>.

⁴ Krzaklewska, E., Sekuła, P., Struzik, J. & Ciaputa, E. (2019). *Działania na rzecz równości płci w nauce. Determinanty nierówności i narzędzia zmiany*. *Alma Mater 208-209*, 60-62.

⁵ EIGE. (2020). *Gender mainstreaming. Poland*. EIGE. <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/countries/poland>.

⁶ RPO. (2018). *Doświadczenie molestowania wśród studentek i studentów. Analiza i zalecenia*. Warszawa: Biuro Rzecznika Praw Obywatelskich. <https://www.rpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/Do%20C5%9Bwiadzczenie%20molestowania%20w%C5%9Br%C3%B3d%20studentek%20i%20student%C3%B3w%2C%202018.pdf>.

⁷ Gerlich, J. (2019). *Molestowanie na polskich uczelniach publicznych*. Warszawa: Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka. <https://www.hfhr.pl/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/%E2%80%9EMolestowanie-na-polskich-uczelniach-publicznych%E2%80%9D-%E2%80%93-raport-HFPC.pdf>.

⁸ Gerlich, J., Jarzmus, K. (2020). *„Być albo nie być” – pracowniczki i pracownicy polskich instytucji artystycznych wobec zagrożenia mobbingiem, molestowaniem i molestowaniem seksualnym*. Warszawa: Helsińska Fundacja Praw Człowieka. <https://www.hfhr.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/byc-albo-nie-byc-21-11.pdf>.

active preventive measures against harassment.^{9,10} Nevertheless, the number of universities with anti-discrimination measures, policies, or procedures in place is still rather small compared to the total number of HEIs in Poland. Finally, GBV in higher education and RPOs is still a taboo topic,¹¹ and as a result there are no specific prosecution or disciplinary measures and no services provided to victims by HEIs.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

Provisions regarding antidiscrimination are provided in this institution's Human Resources Strategy for Researchers and the Action Plan for 2019-2021¹² and in the Recruitment Policy for Research Employees (2021).¹³ Information concerning GBV is included in the Code of Ethics of Researchers (hereinafter the Code of Ethics) and the Internal Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy against Mobbing, Discrimination and Harassment (hereinafter the Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy). While the Code of Ethics is a more general document addressing multiple ethical issues, the Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy addresses more specifically issues of GBV and other forms of violence and discrimination.

Anti-discrimination rules relate to ensuring a gender balance among employees and on the board of directors and to the obligation of employers not to discriminate. However, in the Code of Ethics and Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy more detailed provisions relating to the GBV can be found.

The main actors involved in the process of discrimination prevention and implementing measures include: the institute's leadership (director general, scientific director, scientific and technical director), administrative departments and staff (i.e. Human Resources Department, Research Service and Administration), thematic committees (i.e. Disciplinary Commission, Anti-Mobbing Commission), and equality bodies or the equivalent (i.e. Equality Team, Disciplinary Commissioner, Ombudsperson).

URLs

- › Code of Ethics: https://www.ifj.edu.pl/dla-pracownikow/etyka/Kodeks_Etyki_Pracownika_Naukowego.pdf
- › Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy against Mobbing, Discrimination and Harassment: Not available online

⁹ Teutsch A., Stoch, M., & Kozakoszczak, A. (2017b). *Opracowanie merytoryczne na temat przeciwdziałania dyskryminacji i przemocy motywowanej uprzedzeniami dla studentów, studentek, doktorantów, doktorantek, nauczycieli i nauczycielek szkół wyższych*. Kraków: Fundacja Autonomia.

¹⁰ RPO. (2019, October). Polskie uczelnie powinny skuteczniej walczyć z molestowaniem. *Biuletyn Informacji Publicznej RPO*. <https://bip.brpo.gov.pl/pl/content/rpo-polskie-uczelnie-powinny-skuteczniej-walczyc-z-molestowaniem>

¹¹ ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation. (2020). *Sexual Harassment in the Research and Higher Education Sector: National Policies and Measures in EU Member States and Associated Countries*. Brussels: European Research Area And Innovation Committee. https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/SWGGRI_Sexual-Harassment-in-the-Research-Higher-Ed.-National-Policies-Measures.pdf.

¹² *The Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) at the Henryk Niewodniczański Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences (IFJ PAN) with Respect of The Principles of The European Charter for Researchers and The Code of Conduct for The Recruitment of Researchers Action Plan For 2019-2021*. (2019). Kraków: IFJ PAN. <https://www.ifj.edu.pl/kariera/hrs4r/pdf/strategia-2019.pdf>.

¹³ *Recruitment Policy for Research Employees*. (2021). Kraków: IFJ PAN. <https://www.ifj.edu.pl/kariera/zasady-zatrudnienia/pdf/polityka-rekrutacji.pdf>.

Entry into force: The Code of Ethics came into force in 2017 and the Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy in 2020.

TRAINING

To prevent discrimination, the policies include a statement prohibiting all forms of harassment and discrimination and call for mandatory training on relevant issues for employees and members of the board of directors. Employees have been provided with anti-mobbing training, and basic information is provided on the institution's website on anti-mobbing, discrimination, harassment, equal treatment regulations, and the institutional procedures for filing a complaint and investigating cases.^{14,15,16}

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

None.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies combined cover **two** forms of violence: sexual harassment and gender-based harassment. The Code of Ethics contains a broad statement on harassment, while the Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy covers sexual harassment and gender-based harassment.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harrassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harrassment | |

7Ps covered: The two policies combined cover the **7Ps**. Only the Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy addresses prevalence, prosecution, provision of services, partnership, and policy, while both cover prevention and protection.

¹⁴ <https://www.ifj.edu.pl/dla-pracownikow/komisje/wyciag-rowne-traktowanie.pdf>.

¹⁵ <https://www.ifj.edu.pl/dla-pracownikow/komisje/komisja-antymobbingowa/>.

¹⁶ Zielińska-Golik, I. (2021, February). *Mobbing, dyskryminacja i molestowanie oraz przeciwdziałanie tym zjawiskom*. https://www.ifj.edu.pl/dla-pracownikow/komisje/komisja-antymobbingowa/pdf/Prezentacja_mobbing_dyskryminacja_molestowanie.pdf.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: Jointly, the policies address **all target groups:** academic staff, non-academic staff, and students. The Code of Ethics covers academic staff and students, while the Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy is aimed only at academic and non-academic staff.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: Information not available.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Both policies have procedures in place and in both cases there is **one procedure for all**.

Code of Ethics

The Code of Ethics defines: Who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, responsible persons/units, and outcomes.

Who to contact and how to report: 'A person who has detected misconduct or has a reasonable suspicion that an act incompatible with ethics in science has been committed is obliged to report the problem to the head of the unit where the research is carried out (...) or to the relevant disciplinary spokesperson, and when there is a conflict of interest at the management level, the report should be made to the head of the superior authority (e.g. supervisor). The report should describe the allegation and substantiate it in detail and must include a signature and contact

details. The identity of the person reporting the misconduct (the whistle-blower) is not disclosed until disciplinary proceedings are initiated. If the person making the allegation feels it more appropriate, the report may be submitted to the Science Ethics Committee and specifically to its chairperson, who may ask the person making the allegation for additional information. If the committee decides that, in the light of the circumstances mentioned in the report, the allegation is justified, it is forwarded to the head of the unit in which the alleged offender is employed in order to initiate proceedings. In special cases, the Scientific Ethics Committee may, at its own initiative, refer cases concerning violations of the principles of ethics in science by employees of universities, research institutes, and scientific units of the Polish Academy of Sciences to the competent authorities of these units with a recommendation to conduct investigatory proceedings. Information on the results of this investigation is immediately communicated to the Science Ethics Committee.

Responsible persons/units: Science Ethics Committee.

Investigation procedure: The investigatory proceedings are carried out by the disciplinary spokesperson. If the information provided to the disciplinary spokesperson concerns a gross violation of the principles of ethics in science, the disciplinary officer is required to initiate investigatory proceedings ex officio. In other cases, the initiation of investigatory proceedings take place at the request of the body that appointed the spokesperson. It is essential that the spokesperson be provided with the appropriate operating conditions. The investigatory proceedings should be insightful and meticulous, and be conducted in accordance with the procedures in place in a given institution, with respect for the alleged perpetrator's right to a defence, and with due diligence and objectivity. The investigators should disclose all the circumstances, including those that may give rise to a conflict of interest. All aspects of the investigation must be documented in detail. The person against whom the allegation has been made should be immediately notified when investigatory proceedings have been initiated. They should be given the opportunity to be heard and are entitled to legal aid. An important condition for maintaining the highest standards in these cases is the strict confidentiality of the investigation and limiting the group of people informed about the proceedings, as well as the proper maintenance of documentation in order to protect the persons involved. The necessary disclosure of information to third parties should occur on the condition that such persons are obliged to maintain confidentiality, unless they are already obliged to do so by virtue of their function.

Outcomes: The investigation should conclude with a confidential report containing the findings and recommendations for further proceedings. If the management of the entity concludes, on the basis of the report, that the allegation of misconduct was unfounded, but that it was made in good faith, the proceedings are terminated, and the parties are notified of this. An accused person should have the right to request that it be made public that the charges against him/her have been dropped. If, on the other hand, management determines that the allegations were not made in good faith, then it will take special disciplinary action against the person who made the allegations. If the investigatory proceedings were conducted on the basis of an initiative from the Science Ethics Committee, the results of the investigation are to be forwarded to the committee without undue delay. The purpose of the disciplinary proceedings is to establish whether an alleged act has taken place and to issue a decision depending on this finding. This procedure is conducted - according to the place of employment of the employee – in conformity with the provisions of the Act on the Polish Academy of Sciences of 30 April 2010, the Act on Higher Education of 27 July 2005, and the Act on Research Institutions of 30 April 2010. These provisions regulate in detail how proceedings should be conducted, the content of the judgements issued in the proceedings, possible disciplinary penalties, the appeal procedure against a ruling of the first instance from the

disciplinary commission, the possibility of reopening the proceedings, and how to appeal to a court against the disciplinary rulings.'

The Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy

The Anti-Mobbing and Anti-Discrimination Policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, the description of the investigation, a time frame, responsible persons/units, outcomes, and sanctions.

Who to contact and how to report: 1. Any employee who believes that he or she has been subjected to mobbing or discrimination has the right to submit a written complaint to their employer. 2. The complaint should contain a brief description of the facts by indicating, in particular, the time and place the incident occurred and the type of behaviour that bears the hallmarks of mobbing, discrimination, or harassment, possible evidence to support the facts mentioned, and an indication of the perpetrator or perpetrators of mobbing. 3. Every report should be submitted to the director or the Anti-Mobbing Committee in writing. The employee should sign the complaint and date it by hand. Anonymous complaints will not be considered.

Responsible persons/units: Anti-Mobbing Committee.

Description of investigation and time frame: 4. The committee examines the case within 21 days of the date when a complaint was lodged, and if the circumstances of the case make it impossible to settle it within this period the committee may extend the investigation of the case. 5. The Anti-Mobbing Commission is responsible for case investigation. Minutes are prepared from the meetings of the commission, which are signed by all of its members.

Outcomes: 6. At the end of the investigation, the Anti-Mobbing Commission prepares a decision.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

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